

THE EPISODE OF MURATBAY NIZANOV'S ARTISTIC WORK “ASHIQ BOLMAĞAN KIM BAR”

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Annotaciya: Biz bul maqalamızda házirgi qaraqalpaq ádebiy processiniń rawajlanıwına óziniń hár qıylı janrdáǵı shıǵarmaları menen úlken úles qosıp kiyatırǵan belgili jazıwshı Muratbay Nızanovtıń “Ashıq bolmaǵan kim bar” shıǵarmasındaǵı syujetlik ózgesheliklerge dıqqat qaratqandı maqul kórdik.

Annotation: We have decided to study the episode features of an artistic work “Ashıq bolmaǵan kim bar” by the well-known writer Muratbay Nizanov, who has made a great contribution to the development of the current Karakalpak literary process with his artistic works of various genres in this article.

Аннотация: В этой статье мы решили изучить сюжетные особенности художественного произведения «Ашық болмаған ким бар» известного писателя Муратбая Низанова, внесшего большой вклад в развитие современного каракалпакского литературного процесса своими разножанровыми художественными произведениями.

Gilt sózler: *kórkem shıǵarma, qaharman, obraz, syujet, xarakter.*

Ключевые слова: *литературное произведение, герой, образ, эпизод, характер.*

Keywords: *literary work, hero, image, episode, character.*

There is some information that the term “episode” was used in literature by Carmel and Buano, representatives of the classicism movement who lived in the 17th century. They

adopted this concept from Aristotle, who used it when talking about the legendary heroes of the ancient Greeks.

Episode comes from the French language and means “thing”. An episode is a list or collection of events, events, including the actions of characters, expressed in a work of fiction. The episode is a means of revealing the character, its differences, a set of connections between characters suitable for the representation of specific events.²² This term is sometimes used when analyzing lyrical artistic works.

In very early times, Roman writers used the term “fabula” instead of the word “episode”. Fabula means “telling, explaining”. In the literature of the Soviet countries of the 20th century, the terms episode and fabula were considered synonymous, that is, the direction of all events in a artistic work is called “episode”, and the conflict in artistic work is called “fabula”.²³

So, what we call a fabula is a kind of event. The reason is that there is a fable in every story. Even so, any event could not be a beautiful artistic work. The episode is only in an artistic work. Therefore, episode and fable have different roles.

The episode shows the relationship between the character of the hero and the events that are subordinated to the formation of the character in them. In a literary artistic work, there is always a connection between the story and the character.

In M. Nizanov’s work “Ashiq bolmağan kim bar”²⁴, the author cleverly described the characteristics of human psychology, the very subtle and mysterious aspects of human relationships, and the power of conscience. The episode of the artistic work is similar to the episode of the triangular composition. The reason is that the story is told through flashbacks.

²²Járimbetov Q. Ádebiyattanıwdan sabaqlar. Nókis, «Qaraqalpaqstan», 2012, 23-bet.

²³Мамбетов К. Әдебият теориясы. Нөкис, «Билим», 1995. 94-бет.

²⁴Нызанов М. Ашық болмаған ким бар. Нөкис, «Билим», 2013.

If we focus on its compositional structure, it consists of a prologue and an epilogue, the main event. The main narrative story is told through Jupargul's memories, diary, Nursuliw's diary.

In particular, the divinity related to the feeling of love, the wide-ranging imaginations are artistically presented, and the situations that shake the reader's inner world, enrich his thoughts, warm his heart, melt his hardness and make him regret, are directly rhymed.

The events in this novel, most of the images of the characters are familiar to us, come close to reality, and show the images of people whose appearance is still vivid in most people's minds.

The images of Ismayil, Queen, Kenjamurat, Tilawkhan, and Madiyars in the artistic work, their artistic reflection, kindness, loyalty and justice features directly attracted the reader and made them worthy to learn from him. Ismail's actions, correctness, loyalty, diligence, eloquence, open-heartedness in the artistic work will serve as an example to the students. It is hard to find any mistake on it.

REFERENCES

1. Járimbetov Q. Ádebiyattanıwdan sabaqlar. Nókis, "Qaraqalpaqstan", 2012. 23-bet.
2. Мамбетов К. Әдебият теориясы. Нөкис, «Билим», 1995. 94-бет.
3. Нызанов М. Ашық болмаған ким бар. Нөкис, «Билим», 2013.